

Tool 6

Reflect on your project objectives

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 1 – Prepare), which helps you to reflect on the possible objectives you can achieve through your citizen science project.

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer. If you have any further questions about this template, please contact citizenscience@vub.be.

Step 1. Where in the Venn diagram would you place your research (project)?

Step 2. Describe your (anticipated) research, educational and social impact.

Research objective(s)	Educational objective(s)	Societal impact(s)
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Consequently, if in 2030 you wake up, what do you see in the world around you that shows this change?